

WORLD CONGRESS
ON OSTEOPOROSIS,
OSTEOARTHRITIS AND
MUSCULOSKELETAL
DISEASES

AbstractBook

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THE INFLUENCE OF MORNING STIFFNESS, PAIN, AND FATIGUE ON THE KEY GRIP STRENGTH IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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Objective: To examine the influence of morning stiffness, pain, and fatigue on the key grip strength in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA).

Material and methods: The sample for this prospective cross-sectional study comprised 56 RA patients of both sexes treated at the Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases in Novi Sad, Serbia. After signing the informed consent form, the participants rated their hand pain intensity on the 0–10 VAS Visual Pain Scale and fatigue intensity on a 0–10 scale. The precision key grip strength (kg) was estimated using the Baseline-Mechanical Pinch Gauge dynamometer. The association between the VAS and fatigue scores and the key grip strength in both hands was tested through Spearman's correlation coefficient, while Using the Kruskal Wallis test was conducted to check whether there is a statistically significant difference between the morning stiffness duration and the key grip strength in both hands.

Results: The median VAS and fatigue scores for the sample (average age 63, 92.9% women, all right-handed) were Me=7.00 (IQR=2.0) and Me=7.00 (IQR=3.0), respectively. There was no statistically significant correlation between the VAS score and the key grip strength in the right ($\rho=-0.088$, $p>0.05$) or the left hand ($\rho=-0.140$, $p>0.05$). Similarly, no statistically significant correlation between the fatigue score and the key grip strength in either hand was established (right: $\rho=-0.259$, $p>0.05$; left: $\rho=-0.163$, $p>0.05$). On the other hand, morning stiffness duration was in a statistically significant relationship with the key grip strength of the right hand ($p=0.008$), as well as the left hand ($p=0.001$). Patients in whom morning stiffness lasts up to 30 minutes had the strongest key grip (right hand: Me=7.78, IQR=6.13; left hand: Me=8.75, IQR=5.63). Those with the longest morning stiffness (>60 min) had the weakest right-hand grip (Me=4.00, IQR=6.10; Me=3.16, IQR=5.83).

Conclusion: RA patients who have morning stiffness of longer duration have a weaker key grip in both hands, while pain and fatigue do not affect the key grip strength.

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REHABILITATION PROCESS AFTER TIBIA AND FIBULA FRACTURES IN ADOLESCENTS: A CASE REPORT

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Fractures of both, tibia and fibula, in adolescents are common (5% of all fractures) and generally have good outcomes due to the high healing potential and bone remodeling ability in pediatric patients.

Case Report: A 16-year-old boy was injured in a traffic accident and diagnosed with distal tibia and fibula fractures. Five days after the injury, he underwent surgery (orthopedic repositioning and osteosynthesis). He was referred for outpatient rehabilitation, shortly after surgery, at the Clinic for Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Novi Sad, Serbia. Informed consent was obtained from the patient and his parents, with approval from the Ethics Committee (decision no: 3987-3/2024). Range of motion (ROM) was measured using a goniometer, and muscle strength was assessed weekly with the Manual Muscle Test (MMT). At the initial assessment, the patient used crutches and did not bear weight on the right leg. Swelling (1 cm) was present in the lower leg and foot, and thigh muscle atrophy (1 cm) was noted. ROM in the knee was normal, but only initial dorsiflexion and plantarflexion were possible in the ankle due to pain. The 6-week rehabilitation program included physical modalities (interferential therapy, paraffin therapy) and kinesiotherapy. Treatment goals included reducing pain and swelling, restoring ankle mobility, improving muscle strength, and reintegrating the patient into daily and sports activities. Initially, the patient was non-weight-bearing and used crutches. By the third week, partial weight-bearing (up to 30%) was allowed, with individual kinesiotherapy tailored to the patient's progress. At the end of 6 weeks, the patient was advised to return to daily activities and gradually resume sports, under guidance from a sports physician.

Conclusion: An individually tailored rehabilitation process after tibia and fibula fractures in adolescents leads to complete functional recovery and return to daily activities.